

Evaluation of Biological Properties of Pure Biofine Chemicals and Aroma Substances From Cannabis Sativa Essential Oil

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Abstract

Essential oils are a mixture of bioactive chemicals that are useful to humans as therapeutics and preservatives. The essential oils of *Cannabis sativa* have been tested for their antioxidant, fungicidal, bactericidal and cytotoxic properties. A maximum of 0.035% extraction was found at 110°C. Caryophyllene, trans- α -bergamotene, humulene, and cis- β -farnesene in different percentages were major components to more than 29 major and minor identified in each oil of *C.sativa* via GC-MS analysis. Separation is done using a fractional method. The total phenolic content was found to be 13.42-13.83 and 11.24-14.68 mg GAE/ml; the total flavonoid content was 14.12-14.22 and 10.78-15.39 mg CE/ml, and the estimated content of proanthocyanidin was 8.91-10.46 and 7.16-11.31 mg VE/ml of *C.sativa* essential oil and fractions, respectively. Antioxidant activity was tested with DPPH• intake of 20.55-26.26% essential oil and 37.77% high in F1 of 110°C essential oil. The ability to reduce ferric ions was set at 2.4-2.69 mg/ml, and the maximum reduction potential of 2.78 mg/ml was F5 of 120°C essential oil at 0.3 mg/ml concentration. The high inhibition of linoleic acid peroxidation was shown by F4,

25.67% of 130°C extracted by the essential oil. Antibacterial values 19.33mm, 19.67mm, 19.82mm zone of inhibition and antifungal activity 20.15mm, 22.13mm, 22.26mm zone of inhibition indicated by F1, F5 and F4 of 110°C, 120°C and 130°C extracted oil *Cannabis* essential oils are sequential. Similarly, MBC and MFC are also shown with these components. The concentrations of brine shrimp cytotoxicity 20ppm and 25ppm have been shown by F1 and essential oils collected at 110°C. *Sativa* oil controls cancer and antibacterial properties as used in medicine.